

Looking for Autistic Traits in Human Figure Drawings done by Children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD): A Short Review of Five Selected Published Papers

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Abstract

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a challenging, not yet fully understood, condition associated with neurodevelopmental, mental, or behavioral problems. Its onset takes place in the early developmental period (may not manifest until social demands exceed limited capacities) with persistent deficits in social communication and social interaction, and deficits in social-emotional reciprocity and social relationships. As a neurodevelopmental disorder, ASD impacts the development of the nervous system, leading to slightly different cortical function that, in turn, may affect cognition, conation, emotion, memory, and sensation. The effects of ASD tend to last for an individual's lifetime. Hence, it is important to assess a child for suspected ASD as early as possible so that appropriate follow-up intervention can be provided. For past four to five decades, many ASD-related assessment tools have been developed for the purpose of early identification, diagnostic evaluation and profiling. In this paper, the authors have chosen to review five selected published papers on human figure drawings done by autistic individuals in their attempt to find common autistic traits in these projective drawings to be used as indicators for ASD screening in children.

Key words: Autism Spectrum Disorder, Autistic Traits, Early Identification, Human Figure Drawing

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) or autism for short was originally known as childhood schizophrenia (Cantor, 1988; Cantor et al., 1982) and was often mistaken to be the result of cold parenting due to what was then known as the 'refrigerator mother' complex¹ (Bettelheim, 1950, 1959, 1967). Later, according to Zeldovich (2018), it became 'a set of related developmental disorders, and finally as a spectrum condition with wide-ranging degrees of impairment' (para. 2). The diagnostic criteria of ASD have been changing through the past decades from the time when an Austrian-American psychiatrist and physician, Leo Kanner, first described it in 1943 (Camulli & Goh, 2018).

With the publication of the third edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-III; American Psychiatric Association/APA, 1980), autism was established

with its own separate diagnosis. It was then described it as a pervasive developmental disorder (PDD) in order to distinguish it from schizophrenia. With the subsequent release of the DSM-IV (APA, 1994) and its revised edition of DSM-IV-TR (APA, 2000), autism was categorized as a spectrum disorder, which includes the following: Asperger Disorder, Childhood Disintegrative Disorder (also known as Heller Syndrome), Rett Syndrome, and Pervasive Developmental Disorder-Not Otherwise Specified (PDD-NOS).

Throughout the decade of 1990s and the beginning of the first decade in the new millennium, researchers were focusing on the genetic identification of ASD. With the completion of the Human Genome Project in 2003, according to Zeldovich (2018), many research studies (e.g., Geschwind, 2011; Goldani et al., 2014; Rutter, 2000) attempted to zero in on a list of so-called

¹ This controversial psychological theory postulated that the cause of autism was due to a lack of maternal (figurative) warmth.

autism genes (see Zeliadt, 2017). Studies (e.g., Prandini et al., 2012; Skaar et al., 2005; Wassink et al., 2001) have found thousands of autism-related gene markers, but not all gene markers could link exclusively to autism (Happé, Ronald & Plomin, 2006). In other words, there is no such a thing as autism gene. ‘There are several conditions associated with autism that stem from mutations in a single gene, including Fragile-X Syndrome and Rett Syndrome’ (Zeliadt, 2017, para. 5). However, the number of cases of non-syndromic autism stemming from mutations in any single gene was found to be less than 1 percent (Zeliadt, 2017, 2021). The research findings to date retort the fact that ‘there is no such thing as an *autism gene* — meaning that no gene is consistently mutated in every person with autism ... also does not seem to be any gene that causes autism every time it is mutated’ (Zeliadt, 2017, para. 5). In other words, the attempt to find genetic underpinnings and corresponding treatments for the five conditions specified in the DSM-IV has become rather impossible. Hence, it is best to ‘characterize autism as an all-inclusive diagnosis, ranging from mild to severe’ (Zeliadt, 2017, para. 5).

Tools for Autism Assessment

There is a wide range of informal and formal screening and assessment tools available for professionals to use in the assessment process to determine a diagnosis of ASD based on the diagnostic criteria provided in the DSM-5 (or alternatively, ICD-10² which is widely used in western European countries). The DSM-5 (APA, 2013) has indicated that “an autism diagnosis requires ‘persistent deficits in social communication and social interaction across multiple contexts, as manifested by the following’: deficits in social-emotional reciprocity, in nonverbal communicative behaviors used for social interaction, and in developing, maintaining and understanding relationships” (Hess, 2022, para. 3). As a result, any autism assessment approach will have to put in mind the DSM-5 criteria for ASD identification.

The autism assessment approach may include the following widely used diagnostic tools: Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule-2nd Edition (ADOS-2; Lord et al., 2012), Autism Detection in Early Childhood (ADEC; Young, 2007), Autism Diagnostic Interview-Revised (ADI-R; Lord Rutter, & Le Couteur, 1994), Child Autism Rating Scale-2nd Edition (CARS-2; Schopler et al., 2010), and Social Communication Questionnaire (SCQ; Rutter, Bailey, & Lord, 2003). Other useful ASD diagnostic assessment tools also include the following: Communication and Symbolic Behavior Scales

(CSBS; Wetherby & Prizant, 2003), Gilliam Autism Rating Scale (GARS-3, Gilliam, 2014), Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers (M-CHAT; Robins et al., 2001), Parent’s Evaluation of Development Status (PEDS; PEDStest.com., 2013), and Screening Tool for Autism in Toddlers and Young Children (STAT; Stone & Ousley, 2008).

In addition, professionals assessing or diagnosing children suspected of ASD may also administer cognitive tests, such as Comprehensive Receptive and Expressive Vocabulary Test-3rd Edition (CREVT-3; Wallace & Hammill, 2013) and Oral and Written Language Scales-2nd Edition (OWLS-2; Carrow-Woolfolk, 2011), and other assessments, such as Ages and Stages Questionnaires-3rd Edition (ASQ-3; Squires & Bricker, 2009) and Early Screening Inventory-Revised (ESI-R; Meisels et al., 2008), in order to gather more information about a child’s development.

Besides, one interesting assessment approach is the use of projective drawing techniques (e.g., human figure drawing and house-tree-person drawing) to screen or identify those with ASD. For decades, children’s human figure drawings (HFDs) have been the focus of attention. Lim and Slaughter (2008) argued that HFDs ‘reflect a number of psychological variables including the drawers’ intellectual maturity, personality, thought and emotion (Goodenough, 1926; Koppitz, 1968; Machover, 1949)’ (p. 988). For this main reason, the authors of this paper selected five published papers on human figure drawings done by individuals with ASD for review. Through the review, the authors hoped to find common autistic traits in these projective drawings that could be used as early autism indicators to screen children suspected of having the condition and be referred to professionals for further assessment and follow-up treatment.

Human Figure Drawings (HFDs) to identify Autistic Traits

For a long time since the early 1920s when Goodenough (1926) first introduced drawing as a measure of intelligence, and almost 40 years later, it was popularized by Harris (1963), projective drawing techniques based on human figure drawings (HFD) have captured the attention of clinical and diagnostic professionals. Moreover, over the past six to seven decades, many studies (e.g., Flanagan & Motta, 2007; Gigi, 2016; Matto, Naglieri, & Clausen, 2005; Slansky & Short-DeGraff, 1989) have been published debating about the efficacy, reliability and validity of projective drawing

² ICS-10 is the abbreviation for International Classification of Diseases-10th Edition published by the World Health Organization in 1990.

techniques as clinical assessment tools (also see Motta et al., 1993, for detail). It is not within the scope of this paper to discuss about this issue and readers interested to find out more should consult the papers cited here.

The reason why the authors of this paper have chosen to focus on identifying autistic traits in HFDs instead of other projective drawings, such as a house or a tree drawing, is that they firmly believe children's HFDs reflect the developmental stages that they are likely to be associated with, both cognitive and socialization processes, as postulated by Cox (1993), Freeman (1987), Lim and Slaughter (2008), and Motta et al., (1993).

Photograph 1. Scribbling done on the Whiteboard by a Child with ASD (Courtesy of Crossland)

The authors have selected and reviewed the following five published papers on the use of human figure drawings (HFDs) in identifying autistic traits:

1. Lee, A. & Hobson, R.P. (2006). Drawing self and others: How do children with autism differ from those with learning difficulties? *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 24, 547-565.
2. Lim, H. K., & Slaughter, V. (2008). Brief report: Human figure drawings by children with Asperger's syndrome. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 38(5), 988-994.
3. Bar, I., Gabriely, M. A., Ashkenazi, O., & Shaviv, G. (2011). Autism spectrum disorder as reflected in drawings. *Academic Journal of Creative Art Therapies*, 1(1), 52-56.
4. Papangelo, P., Pinzino, M., Pelagatti, S., Fabbri-Destro, M., & Narzisi, A. (2020). Human figure drawings in children with autism spectrum disorders: a possible window on the inner or the outer world. *Brain Sciences*, 10(6). Article ID: 398.
5. Ivanova, V. (2021). Specifics in children's drawings with autism. *Journal of Intellectual Disability-Diagnosis and Treatment*, 9(4), 368-373.

In the first review of the HFD study done by Lee and Hobson (2006), the two researchers made a comparison of drawings done by 14 subjects with ASD, aged 8 to 15 years, with those done by non-autistic subjects with learning disabilities (LD). They found that HFDs done by children with ASD showed a lack of variety due to their unusual way of thinking about and how they related to other people. When the subjects with ASD were asked to draw a female person, a male person and finally to also draw themselves, there emerged crucial differences between the ASD and LD groups in their HFDs. The LD subjects drew three distinct human figures, but the ASD subjects produced three human figures that varied little from one to the other. The HFDs done by the autistic subjects were just as detailed but they lacked variation. Lee and Hobson (2006) explained that '[T]here is evidence that (autistic) children's sense of individual kinds and characters of people, and their concepts of themselves, are less infused with personal qualities than are those of people without autism – and undifferentiated human figures would be one result' (cited in Jarrett, 2006, para. 3).

In the second review of another HFD study done by Lim and Slaughter (2008), 29 children with Asperger Syndrome (AS) or what Attwood (2014) has termed as ASD Level-1 (ASD-1), and 28 typically developed (TD) children were asked to draw a person, a house and a tree. As reported, there were no significant differences between the two groups on the tree or house drawing scores. However, when it came to the person drawing (or HFD) scores, children with AS (or ASD-1) scored significantly lower than TD children on the person drawing or HFD, using the Koppitz's (1968) scoring system, which involves both developmental and emotional indicators. However, in Lim and Slaughter's (2008) study, 'only the developmental indicators were used as they reflect the accuracy, detail and complexity of the human figures portrayed' (p. 990). Koppitz's (1968) scoring system for HFDs revealed a significant difference between the AS and TD groups, $t(55)=3.13$, $p<0.005$, with the magnitude of the differences in the means, $\eta^2=0.15$. In other words, the AS group produced fewer indicators of developmental maturity in their HFDs, compared to the TD group.

In addition, Buck's (1948) scoring system was also consulted by Lim and Slaughter (2008), and both good and flawed features of HFDs were tabulated. The HFDs done by the AS group showed 'significantly more flaws, $t(55)=2.65$ with $p<0.005$, and fewer good details, $t(55)=2.41$, $p<0.05$, than those done by TD group' (Lim & Slaughter, 2008, p. 991). When the authors of the study correlated Buck's standardized global scores with those from Koppitz's, they found both sets of scores to be highly consistent, $r(56)=0.88$, $p<0.001$, suggesting

that the two scoring systems ‘generated valid independent measures of the developmental sophistication of children HFDs’ (Lim & Slaughter, 2008, p. 991).

Lim and Slaughter (2008) have also found a positive correlation between HFD (Buck’s and Koppitz’s scoring systems) scores and communication subscores on the Vineland Adaptive Behavior Scales (VABS) for the AS group. Firstly, the correlation reliability between VABS Communication Subscale scores and Buck’s global HFD scores just missed its statistical significance, with ‘partial $r(25)=0.37$, $p=0.061$ (two-tailed), but its magnitude of the correlation was nevertheless noteworthy’ (Lim & Slaughter, 2008, p. 991). The partial correlation reliability between VABS Communication Subscale scores and Koppitz’s HFD indicators was significant, with ‘partial $r(25)=0.41$, $p<0.05$ (two-tailed)’ (Lim & Slaughter, 2008, p. 991).

The findings of Lim and Slaughter’s (2008) study suggested that ‘the selective deficit in generating human figure representations may derive from a relative lack of interest in the social world, and/or limited practice in drawing people’ (p. 988) as exhibited by the AS children, who produce less sophisticated HFDs than TD children. AS children are not deficient in their general drawing ability but ‘rather selectively less likely to produce a developmentally advanced high-scoring HFD’ (Lim & Slaughter, 2008, p. 992). According to Lim and Slaughter (2008), there are four factors to account for the AS children’s HFD deficits: Firstly, children with ASD spend less time looking at people (Swettenham et al., 1998) and hence, possess less detailed representations of human beings in HFDs (Lewis & Boucher, 1991). Secondly, unlike TD children, AS children are less motivated or put little effort to produce accurate or detailed HFDs. In fact, AS children show more interest in drawing inanimate objects and/or other objects of their special interests. Thirdly, AS children are less likely to practice HFD than TD peers, and this may result in developmentally less mature HFD produced. Lim and Slaughter (2008) observed that AS children began their HFDs ‘at a location other than the head ... the norm for typical children (Koppitz, 1963)’ (p. 992). Lastly, Lim and Slaughter (2008) felt that the request for an AS child to produce a HFD may create a selective increase in his/her cognitive load, ‘exacerbating any fine motor problems and thereby causing *the child* to produce developmentally less advanced, relatively low scoring HFDs’ (p. 993).

In the next review of a third HFD study carried out by Bar et al. (2011), the research team used the Machover Draw-A-Person (DAP)³ technique to identify typical indicators that characterize the human figures in the autistic population compared with the normal population. In their study, two groups of eight participating subjects aged between 22 and 38 years old were randomly selected: (i) the experimental group consisted of eight individuals diagnosed with ASD, and (ii) the control group consisted of eight typically developed individuals. The subjects were asked to draw themselves on a piece of paper and three assessors reviewed the projective drawings.

Interestingly, the findings of Bar et al.’s (2011) study highlighted two significant differences between the two groups (Bar et al., 2011). Firstly, based on Malchiodi’s (1997) stages of artistic development, the autistic subjects who scored between second and fifth stages were at a significantly lower artistic developmental stage than the typically developed subjects, who scored between fourth and sixth stages. ‘There were significant differences between the two groups, i.e., $t(14) = -4.99$, where $p < 0.0001$, while the average stage of the experimental group was found to be 3.25 ± 0.89 (Mean \pm SD) and that of the control group was 5.25 ± 0.70 ’ (Bar et al., 2011, p. 55). The finding showed that the autistic drawers’ artistic development was scored in the lower stage when compared to the control group. Bar et al. (2011) explained that ‘[S]ince children with ASD have problems developing imaginary schema and they also show little interest in drawing (Emery, 2004), this may explain their less sophisticated drawings’ (p. 55).

Secondly, the autistic subjects drew significantly larger human figures that occupied a bigger area on the paper than those in the control group. ‘Significant differences were found between the two groups in the square area of the human figure drawn, i.e., $t(14) = 6.72$, where $p < 0.0001$ ’ (Bar et al., 2011, p. 54). The average size of human figure drawing was $306.88 \pm$ square centimeter 66.26 (Mean \pm SD) in the experimental group, and $124.90 \pm$ square centimeter 38.42 (Mean \pm SD) in the control group. This finding, according to Bar et al (2011), could be best explained by the experimental group’s ‘lack of interest in the social world (Lim et al., 2008), and also the autistic drawers were more absorbed into the world of their own (Koenig & Levine, 2011)’ (p. 55).

³ The projective drawing technique developed by Machover (1949) – known as Draw-A-Person (DAP) Test – is based on the idea that the human figures drawn on a blank sheet of paper represent those individuals in a drawer’s subconscious mind and

the paper represents the surrounding in which these human figures are.

Bar et al. (2011) argued that the results of their study suggested several difficulties that would characterize the autistic population: (i) mental retardation, and (ii) difficulties in forming connections with the external environment.

In the fourth review of a recent HFD study done by Papangelo et al. (2020) to evaluate the performance of children with ASD on HFDs relative to their typically developed (TD) peers, all the subjects were asked to draw three human figures (man, woman, self-portrait), and in turn, were evaluated with a neuropsychological battery. Their HFDs were scored according to the Maturity Scale, and correlative approaches testing maturity against neuropsychological scores were applied. The findings from Papangelo et al.'s (2020) study showed that children with ASD presented marked deficits in maturity. There was no significant correlation emerged for both experimental and control groups between maturity and the Theory of Mind (ToM) test. Instead, results from the study indicated positive and significant correlations between maturity and the affect recognition test (AR) with group-specific patterns. In the TD subjects, this result regarded drawings of others, but not self-portraits, while an opposite pattern emerged for the ASD subjects, whose sole maturity in self-portraits significantly correlated with the AR scores. The findings suggested that 'the use of HFD tests with individuals with autism may not be used in clinical practices' (Papangelo et al., 2020, p. 1). However, in basic research, HFDs could be used to highlight dependencies between drawing performance and neuropsychological features, thus possibly providing hints on the functioning of autism.

Finally, in the fifth review of another recent HFD study done by Ivanova (2021), 120 children with ASD (whose severity of autism was measured using CARS-2) between ages 3 and 9 years old were involved in HFDs. According to Ivanova (2021), '[T]he peculiarities of sensory perception and perception of one's own body in children with ASD constitute the basis for understanding their cognitive and social development difficulties' (p.368). This, in turn, also concerns the maturation of drawing expressiveness, which according to several studies (e.g., Cannoni, 2005; Crocetti, 2008; Luquet, 2001) is proportional to the maturation of cognitive and emotional functioning. Children with ASD display lower somatosensory perception⁴ than TD children. As a result, inappropriate HFD is an indicator of a strong inhibition of socio-emotional components observed in children with ASD even if they have an adequate intellectual level but show delays in their

drawing development (Frith, 1989/1991; Olivero, 2012).

In Ivanova's (2021) study, she identified six categories of drawings produced by children with ASD (p. 370): '(1) Embryonal-circles (see Figure 1), water, amoeba (see Figure 2); (2) Color spots that cover the human figure or depict a human figure without external borders; (3) Figures and letters (see Figure 3); (4) Human figures fenced as a bubble, a human figure composed with parts of objects body parts (the elements are not connected); (5) Geometric shapes objects (e.g., buildings, streets with marking, residential blocks, strange shells); and (6) Road signs, logos.'

Figure 1. Embryonal-Circles
(Courtesy of Crossland)

Figure 2. An Amoeba
(Courtesy of Crossland)

Figure 3. Figures and Numbers
Courtesy of Crossland

⁴ It refers to the part of the sensory system that concerns with the conscious perception of touch, pressure, pain, temperature,

position, movement, and vibration, which arise from the muscles, joints, skin, and fascia.

In her analysis of the frequency of the drawings, Ivanova (2021) found that most drawings observed fell under the first category, i.e., circles (see Figure 4), embryonic, water) followed by second and third categories (i.e., color spots, numbers and letters).

Figure 4. Repetitive Circle Drawings
(Courtesy of Crossland)

The HFDs produced are without external borders such that the disjointed body parts, partially drawn, seem to be dangling or scattered everywhere on the paper (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Disjointed Body Parts
Courtesy of Crossland

Category 5 drawings are found in children with moderate ASD. However, those with severe and very severe ASD, ‘embryonic drawings and circles, water, color spots and isolated by some other categories are predominant’ (Ivanova, 2021, p. 370). Interestingly, Ivanova (2021) also noted that ‘children in the worst end of the disorder prefer to draw colorful spots, one particular type of drawing dominates, while children in the lighter forms show a sum of all types of categories’ (p. 370). Only in 10 HFDs were human figures painted and often with non-living elements.

From Ivanova’s (2021) study, the findings revealed the following: (1) Children with ASD are significantly less likely to draw a complete human figure, but often with disjointed body parts and one of the parts is an inanimate object; (2) Their HFDs depend on what they mean and not what they see right before them; (3) The HFDs are done more in a stereotypical way than in a communicative and relational way, i.e., ‘the lack of communication affects not only the verbal level but all channels of expression and imaginative processes, as is also evident in the poverty or lack of symbolic play’ (p. 372); and (4) A significant delay in the drawing process of ASD children is obvious, unrelated to the IQ, but rather to social affection (Di Renzo et al., 2017). In her conclusion, Ivanova (2021) reiterated

her findings showed that ‘the relationship of drawing with the level of autistic symptomatology is unrelated to the IQ but rather to sociability and the level of contact’ (p. 372).

Conclusion

In summary, the review of the five selected published papers on HFDs done by individuals with ASD suggests the following key points when using HFDs to identify autistic traits:

1. HFDs done by children with ASD show a lack of variety due to their unusual way of thinking about and how they related to other people.
2. HFDs done by children with ASD are less sophisticated with less detailed representations of human beings.
3. HFDs done by children with ASD show the drawers are at a significantly lower artistic developmental stage than their TD peers.
4. Children with ASD draw significantly larger human figures that occupied a bigger area on the paper than those drawn by their TD peers.
5. Children with ASD show sole maturity in self-portraits that significantly correlated with their Affect Recognition (AR) scores, but present marked maturity deficits in their HFDs when drawing other human figures.
6. Children with ASD show delays in their drawing development unrelated to their IQ, but rather to their social affection, i.e., sociability and the level of contact.
7. Children with ASD are less likely to draw a complete human figure, but often with disjointed body parts and one of the parts is an inanimate object.
8. HFDs done by children with ASD depend on what they mean and not what they see right before them.
9. HFDs are done more in a stereotypical way than in a communicative and relational way.

In a recent study led by Shi et al. (2021), the Chinese research team from Shanghai Jiao Tong University constructed ‘an ASD painting database which contains 478 paintings drawn by ASD individuals and 490 drawn by the TD group’ (p. 1). Through the process of qualitative and quantitative analyses, they found several significant hallmarks in the ASD paintings: composition location, edge completeness, face, repetitive structure, and structuring logic. However, there is still a lack of adequate and reliable data in the current literature related to the analysis of HFDs as well as other projective drawings done by children with ASD. Further research should be encouraged to investigate the efficacy of the developmental and socio-emotional indicators used in scoring the projective drawings to identify autistic drawers. In this way, the authors of this paper hope a better analytical projective drawing technique can be developed to help therapists to identify the

autistic traits in young children for immediate referral and follow-up early intervention.

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